

Co-funded by
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Human Brain Project

EBRAINS CoCreate:

Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to
Improve the Understanding of Brain-related
Disorders

*Research and innovation roadmaps with long-term ambitions
and visions.*

Facilitated by EBRAINS Community Building Team

EBRAINS
Community

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Introducing EBRAINS

EBRAINS is a new digital research infrastructure, created by the EU-funded Human Brain Project, that gathers an extensive range of data and tools for brain related research. EBRAINS will capitalize on the work performed by the Human Brain Project teams in digital neuroscience, brain medicine, and brain-inspired technology, and will take it to the next level.

The EBRAINS ambition

EBRAINS draws on cutting-edge neuroscience, big data, computing, robotics, and related technologies to help translate the latest scientific discoveries into innovation in medicine and industry, for the benefit of patients and society. EBRAINS' ambition is to provide the scientific community at large with an open state-of-the-art capability that fosters collaborative brain science, opens the way to ground-breaking discoveries, and aims to secure Europe's leading position in the dynamically growing field of multidisciplinary brain research and its exploitation.

EBRAINS

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Method

The **EBRAINS Community** is being built with and for the people developing, using, supporting, and benefiting from the EBRAINS Research Infrastructure, with an interdisciplinary and inclusive focus. In this context, the **EBRAINS CoCreate** process is a strategic community engagement process, which facilitates multi-actor collaboration on research and innovation roadmaps.

Research and innovation (R&I) agendas are generated at many different scales and levels, and by many different bodies, including the European Commission, governments, research agencies, funders, institutions, and individual researchers. A known tendency in this setup is that the scope is often limited by institutional thinking, disciplinary boundaries, or special interests. This leaves a need for defining research agendas across fields and actors, thereby defining more comprehensive and less biased priorities or directions for R&I programmes or projects.

EBRAINS CoCreate builds on the method of Open Research Agenda Setting (ORAS) which recognises the benefits of engaging multi-actors including civil society organisations, patient organisations, and governance bodies in R&I development alongside scientific and technological experts. The resulting research agendas will in turn include visions or problems that societal actors find important, which strengthens and legitimises the selection of research priorities.

The **EBRAINS CoCreate Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-related Disorders** process is made up of four workshops arranged from May 2023 to June 2023 with the following set-up:

The **EBRAINS CoCreate Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-related Disorders** aims to:

- 1) Identify shared long-term ambitions within the areas of disorder identification and treatment.
- 2) Create roadmaps that allow the ambitions to evolve into tangible goals, tracks, and steps.
- 3) Identify opportunities to realise the R&I roadmaps.

Introducing the vision

Integrating Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders

EBRAINS CoCreate is a forward looking cocreation process that delivers roadmaps of visionary science and innovation targets that are important for EBRAINS as an infrastructure and for the multi-actor and interdisciplinary environment around it. The vision in a CoCreate is a societally beneficial one and, accordingly, the roadmap should lead towards positive impacts for society and the individual citizen. A roadmap divides the realisation of the vision up into a stepwise process and identifies needed collaborators and funding paths for at least the first steps.

This EBRAINS CoCreate aims to address the issue of the availability of non-invasive screening methodologies towards brain-related disorders. Epidemiology involving various factors such as lifestyle, phenotypes, environmental exposure, and brain disorders can provide correlations as a starting point for new research on causality and prevention. Adding to this, access to more and improved non-invasive biomarkers such as genotypes and brain scanning methods may give promises of effective screenings. In combination, they give a promise of earlier and better detection, prediction, and prognosis, and of increase in causality research.

With the development and evolution of non-invasive biomarkers for brain related disorders, epidemiology has extended its role in the understanding of brain function. The field of neuroscience benefits from epidemiological studies by gaining a better understanding of the complex interplay between genetics, lifestyle factors, and environmental exposures in the development of neurological disorders such as Alzheimer's Disease and Parkinson's Disease. Non-invasive biomarkers extend the knowledge base of an epidemiological analysis by elucidating the risk factors associated with a disease, such as age and socio-economic status associating this with, for example, neural activity, and brain function. Non-invasive biomarkers in neuroscience measure indicators or substances outside the body without the need for invasive procedures, such as electroencephalograph (EEG). Slightly more invasive biomarkers, such as, blood tests to identify changes in the brain to detect, for example, Alzheimer's disease should be able to extend epidemiological analysis to provide indirect or second level analysis of brain function to support the direct or primary level neuroscience research.

The EBRIANS CoCreate workshop series on Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders worked towards developing a roadmap that integrates the availability of non-invasive biomarkers with improved epidemiology. The participants of the workshop have partaken in creating a roadmap that researchers and innovators can use to develop new focused projects. The goal of this initiative is to improve the overall well-being of citizens by being better at early detection, diagnosis, prognosis, and prevention, and ultimately at treating and curing brain-related disorders.

The vision for this EBRAINS Cocreate is far-reaching and ambitious. But there are inherent challenges. By nature, epidemiological correlations are far from predictable, and they have their strengths in the exploration for yet unseen connections between internal and external factors and the development of disease. Roadmapping for development of such activities can point out fields for exploration and improvement and

can identify weaknesses and roadblocks that needs to be confronted. Thus, rather than a distinct map, the outcome of this EBRAINS Cocreate rather is a sketch of needs and destinations. The map must be produced throughout the evolutionary process. It is the hope that such needs and destinations can motivate further avenues for exploration towards improved neuroepidemiology based on availability of new biomarkers.

The Roadmap

The report represents the overall roadmap towards integrating epidemiology and non-invasive biomarkers to improve the understanding of brain-related disorders. During the workshop series held in May-June 2023, six overarching sub-topics were identified and developed. The sub-topics consist of proposed actions to reach the overall vision of integrating epidemiology and non-invasive biomarkers, and these form the foundation of the roadmap. Each sub-topic has an introductory text followed by a set of actions representing the major steps or milestones needed to reach the vision. Each action includes a challenge- and solutions overview, as well as a description of the required collaborators and resources. Each sub-topic ends with a summary highlighting the key points and the potential outcomes achievable through the implementation of the identified actions. The roadmap should not be considered as a concluded path, but rather as the catalyst to initiate discussions and efforts aimed at pioneering a new paradigm in neuro-epidemiology.

Sub-topics:

- 1) Review and gap analysis of epidemiology and screening
- 2) New data sources and biomarker opportunities
- 3) Solving ethical issues in new biomarkers and epidemiology
- 4) Integrating biomarkers and epidemiology
- 5) Biomarker big data for early detection
- 6) Pathways to practical outcomes of epidemiology.

Roadmap illustration

2023 --- Ramp-up phase --- Proof-of-concept --- Stage of implementation --- 2043

Review and gap analysis of epidemiology and screening

New data sources and biomarker opportunities

Solving ethical issues in new biomarkers and epidemiology

Integrating biomarkers and epidemiology

Biomarker big data for early detection

Pathways to practical outcomes of epidemiology

Visionary Narrative: A possible future in year 2035?

Before delving deeper into the roadmap, a potential future shaped by its careful realisation has been envisioned through a visionary narrative. The visionary narrative envisions a decade of collaborative efforts in clinical neuroscience, spotlighting international partnerships and technological breakthroughs where the dynamic potential arises from the convergence of society, environment, and biology when the approach to brain health is redefined. It draws attention to innovation, data-driven progress, and the transformative impact of collective collaboration on shaping the future.

Clinical neuroscience was strengthened considerably after an international collaboration on development of a diversity of indicators and biomarkers had been established in 2025 and executed in the following decade. The aim had been clear – to make it possible to produce statistically strong correlations between social, environmental, and biological factors and the risk for brain-related disorders, based on strengthened neuroepidemiology.

The international collaboration had been backed up by public as well as private funders and was based on a targeted long-term strategy. This was organisationally arranged as so-called open coordination actions – funded projects should be open for voluntary contributions from any type of actor that could help reaching the targets of the action.

An early set of actions focused on laying the foundation. Scanning of existing epidemiological knowledge was performed, as well as a gap analysis identifying white/unexplored fields on the knowledge map. Money should not be the only determinant but should be used rationally, and an economic model for cost and benefit analysis was developed to help focus on societally important topics. To avoid duplication or needless competition, a mapping of possible synergies was done to make use of existing cross-national infrastructures, including the EBRAINS infrastructure and the EBRAINS Community, for this kind of research and open coordination.

Data acquisition and availability is key to this kind of research, and a range of projects focused on expansion of the available data to provide new options for insights. Establishment of Open and FAIR data (data which meet principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) collaboration and management environments was established by a few projects with operational collaboration on data at the centre. Exploitation of opportunities in new data sources – social media, e-patient records, etc. – was a large area of efforts, with methodological projects, experiments, and mainstreaming planning. Likewise, investments were made in establishing collaboration across neuroscience and other scientific fields, including social science, psychology, and environmental science, on development of relevant indicators followed by investments in data production. With clinical e-records proliferating across countries a set of projects were developing methods, organisational solutions, and standards for improved clinical data collection.

Biomarkers on the one hand often are the result of new insights, but on the other hand, also can be developed by targeted research. Review and strengthening of research on key symptoms and their related biomarkers were therefore a fundamental activity for targeted biomarker development making, of course, use of AI for pattern recognition. Strategic investments in biomarker technology development, including wearable technologies for longitudinal biomarker-based data collection, logically followed. For proper use of biomarker

signals an innovative approach to symptoms assessment scale harmonisation was developed. All put together, the foundation for several projects validating new biomarkers was laid out.

Development of epidemiological analysis tools sensitive to the diversity among human beings was an aim from the start. Epidemiology becomes far more useful if the resolution towards diversity and variance is high. Likewise, sensitivity to early signals of evolving disease makes early screening and detection possible, so efforts were put into developing tools for identifying pre-disease change in the brain.

One thing is science, another thing is implementation. The international collaboration acknowledged early on the need for preparing for the embedding of the insights into clinical and organisational follow-up. Developing new approaches to screening and early detection, based on epidemiological insights, was thus an analytical and dialogical effort that involved organisational and participatory expertise and activities. Societal non-compliance is a 'show-killer', and a guiding and policy developing set of actions were set up on ethics, acceptability, public engagement, and combating stigma – a field of investment that was seen as a precondition for effective strategies. The relevance of such activities becomes clear when looking at the possible data errors that originate from stigma as a systematic error source. This may simply be because providing consent and consenting to allowing an existing ailment or the potential for a future ailment, such as, dementia to be diagnosed, may be hindered as there is a risk of real consequences of stigmatisation for the individual. Consequently, a range of awareness creation activities on brain-related disorders and sensitisation as a basis for more engagement in research were initiated by the involved nations.

Interestingly, the persons behind this endeavour were able to look several years ahead. Developing long-term policy support for this new paradigm would not be easy because of the rather long time from finding a correlation until an implementable practice would be developed. This is not new – the current extensive lead time between correlation and implementation in the practice awareness of creation activities will result in long term gains. A set of communication activities were long-term funded to ensure that the efforts would not be wasted, and that patience was installed.

The result of this grand endeavour has been a new paradigm for neuroepidemiology, which builds on established traditions in the field, and adds a new dimension of disease symptoms, indicators, and biomarkers. The result was a remarkable improvement of targeted research in causality, in early detection and prevention of brain-related diseases. However, how do you measure the impacts of building a foundation? Is it the rise of a house that is the success criterion, or is it the options for new networks, talks, ideas, innovations, policies, investments - new prospects for the future that the house makes possible when it is populated with engaged and inspired guests?

1. Review and gap analysis of epidemiology and screening

Finding the blank spots on the epidemiological map. What is state of the art in the epidemiology of brain health? What are areas that could or should be explored as consequence of having access to new data sources and biomarkers? Is existing data being used well-enough in the epidemiology of brain health? What can be learned from other areas of epidemiology?

Introduction

In this sub-topic, we delve into the intricacies of epidemiology and screening within the domain of brain health. Our goal is to reveal unexplored avenues and address gaps in our current understanding of brain-related disorders.

We begin by charting the current landscape of brain health epidemiology, shedding light on areas that demand further investigation. This prompts us to question the effectiveness of our existing tracking and intervention strategies in this evolving field. With the emergence of innovative data sources and biomarkers, we assess the potential for their integration. How can these tools enrich our insights into brain health? What novel perspectives can they offer, and how might they reshape our approach to interventions? A key component of our exploration involves evaluating the optimal use of existing data sources. Are we maximizing their potential? By scrutinizing our current practices, we seek to enhance the precision of our insights.

Drawing inspiration from broader epidemiological disciplines, we aim to integrate insights and strategies. This integration can guide us in adapting successful methodologies to the complicated realm of brain health. This sub-topic outlines the key challenges in this field and proposes actions to address these challenges, with the goal of advancing our understanding and improving outcomes for individuals affected by brain-related disorders. Each action offers an approach to driving progress and improving outcomes in this complex field. Through increased awareness, streamlined data collection, nuanced strategies to combat stigma, and collaborative exploration of biomarkers, these actions collectively contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of brain-related disorders.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Action: Data collection and extensive gap analysis

Challenge overview: Epidemiology on brain-related disorders is highly deficient (there is a backlog in comparison to other fields of diseases/organ systems).

Solution overview:

- Filling out forms' pre-consultation, relieving time-constraint on clinicians.
- Extensive gap analysis, including on invisible data on brain-related disorders at different levels (molecular, cellular, environmental etc.).
- Clinicians on possibilities in clinical context: time-pressure, reduced data acquisition due to patients' cooperation/compliance.
- Researchers on what is needed for their research hypotheses.
- Data analysts: informing about data structure/hierarchy.
- National registers: feasibility of identifying epidemiological relevant data e.g., in existing registers or setting up a new register (such as the Dutch Brain Research Registry for the recruitment of participants¹, Brain Tumor Epidemiology Consortium², Traumatic Brain Injury Veterans Health Registry³, Dementia registries across the globe⁴).
- Develop wearable devices, or collaborate with groups with existing wearable devices, to monitor different parameters (temp, blood pressure, circadian rhythm, pulse etc.) and provide it to patients free in the hospital home setting. E.g., already available measure sleep patterns and mild cognitive impairment (MCI)⁵, use wearables to identify a pre dementia phase by age, cognitive tests, sleep & heart rate variability (HRV)⁶.

Collaborators include:

- Representatives of national registers.

- Clinicians from different institutes.
- Researchers from different groups.
- Data analysts.

Characterisation of the action: This action involves improving data collection and analysis related to brain-related disorders through collaboration with relevant stakeholders and the implementation of new data collection methods. This can include initiatives such as developing standardized data collection forms for pre-consultation, providing training for clinicians on efficient data collection methods, and collaborating with researchers and data analysts to ensure that collected data is useful for research purposes.

Resources: Funding for data collection initiatives, training for clinicians and researchers, technology for effective data analysis.

Action: Sensitisation: Advancing brain disorder awareness and collaboration initiative

Challenge overview: A new field within Brain-related disorders.

Efforts are rising and already existent, yet to be sufficiently represented within studies, specialised communities, and platforms for exchange. This manifests itself among others as the following challenges.

Solution overview: Increase awareness and understanding of brain-related disorders through education, outreach, and collaboration.

Collaborators include: Medical professionals, researchers, patient advocacy groups, government agencies – European Commission Lifelong Learning⁷.

Characterisation of the action: This action involves increasing awareness and understanding of brain-related disorders through various means such as education, outreach, and collaboration with relevant stakeholders. This can include initiatives such as public awareness campaigns, educational materials for medical professionals and patients, and collaborative research projects to better understand and address brain-related disorders.

Resources: Funding for educational materials, outreach programs, and collaborative initiatives.

Action: Dismantling stigma in brain-related disorders through collaborative data empowerment

Challenge overview: A diagnosis of any brain-related disorder can entail stigmatisation on many levels. First, even the diagnosis might solely relate to a specific population, such as accessibility of consultation and willingness to make use of it. In addition, if a diagnosis is received, patients may not only face societal stigmatisation and shame, but they may also experience increased economical constraints. For instance, the use of biomarkers, genetic profiling and identification of environmental factors have resulted in some at risk patients being offered less favourable co-payment rates or less favourable health insurance policies. Furthermore, certain occupations require a simplified record with regards to certain diseases - most of which are brain-related and thereby results in limiting the opportunity for counselling. Hence, we might face systematic data error.

Solution overview:

- Specifically determine but also restrict bilateral information flow during data acquisition.
- Sharing ERC -The Scientific Council's Working Group: to identify how to support such an endeavour of data sources and biomarker opportunities.
 - CB & CDx Europe summit is annual 2024 in March next year it will be held in Boston⁸.
 - A goal will be to develop joint neuroscience and epidemiology paper to identify biomarkers relevant to epidemiology.

Collaborators include:

- Seek collaborators who will assist in developing national programmes to identify gaps in knowledge.
- Gaps in knowledge: "Forums could include the creation of workshops and advocating for conferences in epidemiology and/or neuroscience to create a neuro epidemiological section. The focus could be to

discuss possible causes for the limitations related to epidemiological research in relation to neuroscience and to identify possible pathways forward.

- Explore further the role that industry could have in assisting with neuroscience and epidemiology collaboration in determining non-invasive biomarkers. For example, if it is a spatial navigation tool for Alzheimer would there have to be a user-friendly device which accounts for different languages and level of computer literacy.

Action: Identifying benefits

Identify specific examples of using epidemiology and identifying the methodology which will be used. This then must be considered in relation to any neuroscientific/neurology methods and ensure that they are compatible. This would require consensus on appropriate use of the methodologies which would involve a multidisciplinary workshop/conference/etc.

Challenge overview: To be able to sketch a more comprehensive picture of a disease and identify risk factors, and reliable biomarkers on the large scale. This would require identifying which elements are required i.e., what would be a relevant comprehensive picture of the disease what is required for each disease or is there a type of template which could be developed as a guide to undertake the process.

Solution overview: See other groups.

¹ <https://alz-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/trc2.12132>

² <https://sites.usc.edu/brainumorcause/about/>

³ <https://www.publichealth.va.gov/epidemiology/reports/oefoifond/health-care-utilization/tbi-registry.asp>

⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6872163/>

⁵ Kimura N et al. Association of modifiable lifestyle factors with cortical amyloid burden and cerebral glucose metabolism in older adults with mild cognitive impairment. <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jamanetworkopen/fullarticle/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.5719>

⁶ Saif N et al. Feasibility of using a wearable biosensor device in patients at risk for Alzheimer's disease dementia. <http://europepmc.org/abstract/MED/32236399>

⁷ <https://illplatform.eu/>

⁸ <https://cdx-europe.com/>

Summary

In summary, this sub-topic delves into the topic of brain health epidemiology and screening, aiming to uncover untapped avenues and bridge gaps in our knowledge of brain-related disorders. This is done by suggesting actions that dissect the current landscape of brain health epidemiology, exposing areas that demand further investigation and challenging our understanding of the efficacy of our existing strategies for tracking and intervention.

With the introduction of innovative data sources and biomarkers, this section proposes actions that ensure their integration, shedding light on how these tools can enhance our understanding of brain health and reshape our approach to interventions. The sub-topic emphasizes the need to maximise the use of existing data sources and outlines strategies to achieve precision and depth in insights.

Inspired by broader epidemiological practices, this sub-topic also advocates for the integration of insights and methodologies from related disciplines. By uniting successful strategies from various epidemiological fields, the complex domain of brain health can benefit from shared knowledge and experience.

The proposed actions address the core challenges in this area and offer practical approaches to drive progress. Through actions that promote extensive data collection and analysis, advance awareness and collaboration initiatives, tackle stigma, and identify benefits, this sub-topic aims to advance our comprehension of brain-related disorders and improve outcomes for individuals affected by them. Collectively, these actions contribute to a more holistic and informed understanding of brain health, laying a foundation for more effective interventions and strategies in this complex and critical field.

2. New data sources and biomarker opportunities

New technological advances can give access to new biomarkers, which provide new types of data. Patient records have become more comprehensive, accessible, and easier to analyse. How should structures be built to take advantage of this?

Introduction

The emergence of new data sources has revolutionised biomarker research, offering unprecedented opportunities for discovery and analysis. Integrating diverse data streams from wearable devices, genomics, and social media enables researchers to uncover valuable insights and identify novel biomarkers with greater precision. These new data sources hold the potential to transform healthcare by enabling real-time monitoring, personalised interventions, and advancements in precision medicine.

Effective data management is crucial for maximising the potential of these new data sources. By implementing robust data management practices, researchers can ensure that data is collected, stored, and analysed in a manner that is consistent, reliable, and secure. This can include the use of standardised data collection protocols, secure storage solutions, and advanced analytical tools to extract meaningful insights from complex datasets.

This sub-topic provides a brief introduction to the proposed actions related to new data sources and biomarker opportunities, with a focus on the importance of effective data management. By leveraging the power of new data sources and implementing robust data management practices, researchers can unlock new opportunities for discovery and innovation in the field of biomarker research.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Action: Prospective FAIR data management plan

Challenge overview: Prospective (Pre-acquisition) management plan design

Solution overview:

- Prospective FAIR data management plan with proactive curation harmonized within.
- National nodes and internationally.
- Develop a white paper on the FAIR data management plan.
- Conduct studies to define data structures archetypes and options.

Collaborators include: EBRAINS, INCF (International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility), Nordic MEG Hub
In the development of the white paper call for people interested in the topic. Subgroups national, EU, rest of the world.

Characterisation of the action: This action involves developing a prospective FAIR data management plan with proactive curation that is harmonised within national nodes and internationally. This can include initiatives such as developing a white paper on FAIR data management plan; conducting studies to define data structures archetypes and options; and collaborating with relevant stakeholders such as EBRAINS and INCF.

Action: Multimodal and multiscale data integration

Challenge overview: Multiscale and multimodal data harmonisation, interoperability, and integration.

Solution overview:

- Multimodal neuroscience data integration (FAIR ontology/metadata/brain atlas integration).
- Combine structural/morphological, functional, metabolic, -omics etc. data).
- Data harmonisation and interoperability from e.g., new/old sensors (e.g., EEG-MEG-osMEG (Electroencephalograph- magnetoencephalography- on scalp magnetoencephalography), 3TMRI/7T MRI).
- Collaboration between the scientific community and AI developers to develop a programme which will enable integration.

Collaborators include: EBRAINS, The Virtual Brain, Nordic MEG Hub, neuroscientists and AI developers.

Resources: EBRAINS and associate members - institutes, universities.

Action: Identification or re-identification of key symptoms of brain-related disorders and their biomarkers

Challenge overview:

- Given the progress in the development of measuring/recording devices, the availability and increasing coverage in society, and the emergence of opportunities for analysing big data (incl. cloud technologies) with the identification of key markers of state/conditions (functions, mental disorders, psychosis, imbalances) in dynamics.
- Shift from simple markers (EEG (electro-encephalography), fMRI (functional magnetic resonance imaging), optical imaging, biochemical, and such as, undertaking population-based studies to determine the Utility of EEG Activation Procedures in Epilepsy and its association with sleep in younger people) to complex markers that characterise temporal-spatial units (structure-function units - networks, units of neural circuit operations, complex).
- Spatial connectivity (network activity patterns for brain structures-behaviours).
- Building of the human brain models (using structural, functional metabolic data) - from a healthy brain (new definitions for Health and Disorders).

Solution overview: Develop systems in which this type of action can be developed. Because the collaborations among diverse research groups regarding epidemiology, neuroscience, AI development, which includes non-invasive biomarker technology, is being developed, then this also has to be established as a fundamental approach within the university system and the development of new researchers, i.e., education must shift to incorporate these cross disciplinary approaches even at the undergraduate level. The broad view is to encourage epidemiology neuroscience departments with undergraduate courses so it will encourage new researchers to come into research with this mind set. USA have several such departments (examples include Columbia University, Harvard University, and New York University), although this could be extended further to be even more inclusive. It is not clear whether such departments exist in Europe.

Collaborators include: EBRAINS and associate members as well as institutes and universities.

Characterisation of the action: A key action is therefore to expand the focus within universities to develop new hybrid education and training, not only for epidemiology and neuroscience, it should also incorporate AI development. In association with this there would be a research group incorporating all of the specialisations which work on developing new hybrid research. For example, in the case of new non-invasive biomarkers, they can develop standardised methods for working in this hybrid group. To achieve this, interested parties can either develop a working group which could be global or create hybrid conferences, or identify research possibilities in research funding such as Horizon in the European Union (EU). For example, in using the non-invasive biomarker that is being developed in Alzheimer's detection using voice and language, the AI technology has been developed to recognise change in a person's use of language. The neuroscientist would identify what changes occur which constitute possible deterioration in language due to Alzheimer's Disease (AD). The epidemiologist would be able to contribute in terms of perhaps cultural differences in the use of the device, issues related to educational standards i.e., if the person would have the skills to use the device, etc.

Resources: EBRAINS and associate members, institutes, universities, EU.

Action: Assess the impact of the environment in the development of a healthy brain and/or mental and stress related disorders

Challenge overview:

- Need to identify NEW Environmental markers, such as, quality of life markers. How to identify, describe, evaluate the objectivity of obtaining information, data, and evaluate their contribution to the development of a healthy brain and the development of mental disorders and stress related disorders.
- Stakeholder identification.

Solution overview:

- Deploy the use of biosensors to monitor the effects of environment, such as, quality of life (environmental data), as potential triggers of stress- and/or mental-related disorders.
- Identify stakeholders and not only those who would have written papers, so interest groups e.g., not for profits Alzheimer's Association
- Determine which are the relevant environmental markers and create workshops and conference subgroups and other avenues to disseminate and discuss the epidemiologist role in incorporating the findings into neuroscience research.

New data sources and biomarker opportunities:

- CB & CDx Europe summit is annual 2024 in March - next year it will be in Boston: <https://cdx-europe.com/>
- Develop a joint neuroscience and epidemiology paper identifying biomarkers relevant to both disciplines.

Collaborators include: EBRAINS, The Virtual Brain, Nordic MEG Hub, other EU Initiatives -neuroscientists & epidemiologists engaged in the research into markers, interest groups.

Characterisation of the action: This action involves assessing the impact of environmental factors on brain health and mental disorders through the deployment of biosensors and collaboration with relevant stakeholders. This can include initiatives such as monitoring environmental data as potential triggers for stress- and/or mental-related disorders, identifying relevant environmental markers through workshops and conference subgroups, and collaborating with interest groups such as not-for-profit organisations.

Resources: Funding for biosensor deployment, workshops, and collaborative initiatives.

Action: Combinatorial challenge of representation communication and analysis of complex datasets

Challenge overview: Challenge of communication due to language barriers to have all information represented from complex datasets that may be lost due to AI interoperability (Language to machine readable format).

Solution overview:

- Interaction of representatives from all involved stakeholder's production of instruments aimed at increasing knowledge in the general population, as well as knowledge dissemination to data integration regarding biomarkers.
- Identify what are the barriers to integrating information from different biomarkers through workshops, conferences, etc.
- Provide funding to explore these issues.

Collaborators include: EBRAINS, The Virtual Brain, Nordic MEG Hub, other EU Initiatives.

Exploring biomarker complementarity with AI developers, neuroscience, and biomarker developers.

Action: Cost and benefit analysis

Challenge overview: If, and when, the actions described here are effectuated, cost and benefit analysis must be at the core.

Solution overview:

- Identify what the cost centres are.
- How much does it cost to finance each cost centres, e.g., hardware, laboratories needed to be built, human resources, what kind of talents do we need, how much money do we need to pay their salaries, office costs, operating costs, fixtures overheads.
- Where are we going to get the funding to finance all these cost centres.
- What are the benefits that this non-invasive biomarker can bring to the table?
- Are these potential benefits justifying the costs that are to be invested?

- If the cost/benefits ratio is negative, then this project does not justify.
- If the cost/benefits ratio is positive, then how much is the ratio? A scale must be drawn.
- What is the benchmark to measure the success/ failure of this project?

Collaborators include: Financial analysts, project managers.

Characterisation of the action: This action involves conducting a cost-benefit analysis to determine whether the potential benefits of this project justify its costs. This can include identifying cost centres such as hardware and human resources; determining how much it will cost to finance these cost centres; identifying potential funding sources; assessing potential benefits; calculating a cost/benefit ratio; and establishing a benchmark for measuring success or failure.

Resources: Funding for financial analysis.

Summary

In conclusion, the emergence of novel data sources has ushered in a transformative era for biomarker research, promising remarkable potential for insight and innovation. By leveraging diverse streams from wearable technology, genomics, and social media, researchers will be able to develop novel insights with even greater precision. These new data sources hold the key to new advances in healthcare through real-time monitoring, personalized interventions, and advancements in precision medicine.

The effective management of these data sources is paramount for maximizing their potential. By adopting robust data management practices, researchers can ensure consistency, reliability, and security throughout the data lifecycle. This entails standardized collection protocols, secure storage solutions, and sophisticated analytical tools for interpreting intricate datasets.

The actions in this sub-topic have outlined a series of proposed actions in the realm of new data sources and biomarker opportunities, with a central focus on the imperative of adept data management. By harnessing the capabilities of these data sources and implementing robust data management strategies, researchers may be able to make new discoveries and innovations within the field of biomarker research.

These actions also delve into the identification of environmental markers, the critical assessment of costs and benefits, the pursuit of FAIR data management practices, multimodal data integration, effective communication, and the identification of key symptoms and biomarkers for brain-related disorders. By fostering cross-disciplinary collaborations, promoting hybrid education, and creating platforms for knowledge exchange, these actions aim to synergize expertise and drive forward the understanding of brain health and mental disorders.

3. Solving ethical issues in new biomarkers and epidemiology

Big data sets and new types of biomarkers provide new ethical challenges. How do we understand disease? What does it mean for a biomarker to be non-invasive? How can the needed ethical safeguards be developed and implemented?

Introduction

Technological advances have allowed medicine and research to continuously penetrate deeper into physiology and furthered understanding in how they relate to certain diseases. The integration of big data and novel biomarkers has emerged, promising remarkable potential. However, as we venture deeper into this new terrain, a host of ethical questions arises. How do we redefine disease considering these new measurements? What truly constitutes a non-invasive biomarker? How can we craft and implement ethical safeguards that preserve both progress and integrity?

This sub-topic embarks on a compelling exploration of the ethical dimensions inherent in this new paradigm of integrating epidemiology and non-invasive biomarkers. Entering this paradigm, the nuances of biomarkers and epidemiology intersect with ethical considerations, thereby charting a course that ensures responsible and meaningful advancement. As we dive into the heart of this discussion, the significance of public discourse cannot be overstated. New depths of measurements and monitoring necessitate open conversations about their implications and regulations. We contemplate the essence of biomarkers and their implications, particularly in the multifaceted domain of brain health.

A central theme that emerges is the challenge of responsible data sharing. With the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) setting the tone, we delve into the complexities of harmonizing data sharing practices across borders. Collaboration at both national and European levels is proposed, cultivating a framework that respects individual privacy while fostering collaborative research. In parallel, the imperative of informed consent takes centre stage. The journey towards ethically sound biomarker utilization necessitates the active participation of patients and society. We explore avenues to make informed consent more accessible and inclusive, empowering individuals with the knowledge to make meaningful decisions about their data. Platforms such as EBRAINS Community and living labs become crucial tools to bridge the gap between research and engagement.

This sub-topic aims to start the dialogue about the ethical considerations that are inevitably woven into the field of biomarkers and epidemiology. We start the discussions about scrutinizing definitions, the security of data-sharing frameworks, and elevating the significance of informed engagement. Our endeavour is to navigate the intricate landscape where innovation converges with ethics, ensuring that our progress towards medical understanding is not only profound but also principled.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Action: Informed consent

Challenge overview: Ensuring that patients understand the implications of their data being used in research and have given their informed consent (It should include consent for the preservation of data for future unidentified research and the extent and limitations involved in the giving of such consent).

Solution overview:

- Have all-inclusive-friendly language for Informed consent.
- Provide education to increase the general level of understanding of why it is useful to share the medical data.
- Iterate over living labs to back and support standpoint of importance of informed consent/GDPR.
- Education: facilitated for example via EBRAINS Community.

Collaborators include: Educational institutions, research community, EBRAINS, patient organisations.

Action: Non-invasive Biomarkers definition

EBRAINS CoCreate: Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-related Disorders

May – June 2023

Challenge overview: One challenge is the discovery and validation of non-invasive biomarkers. Over the past 10 years, studies have been able to identify and validate biomarker candidates, but this process can be difficult and time-consuming (Proteomic discovery of non-invasive biomarkers of localized ... – Nature: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41585-021-00500-1>)

Solution overview:

- Define stages of what non-invasive biomarkers are.
- Determine the level of invasiveness from biological to societal concerns e.g., Identification of persons within a social group especially if it suggests inclusion within a social group which for some members within society is associated with stigmatisation. Also, track and analyse different levels of biomarkers: firstly, general Level1, then Level2 which is more specific and proceed with targeted biomarkers, and then Level3 which has even more specific biomarkers. Also consider Level0 for pre-diseases. The defining procedure would be continuous integration / continuous delivery (CI/CD).
- Invest in research to make progress in finding new biomarkers.
- Clinical implementation of biomarkers.
- Inspiration: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41746-022-00583-z>

Collaborators include: Research institutions and universities and clinics.

Action: Ethical share of data across EU

Challenge overview: Another challenge is the regulatory landscape for biomarkers. The use of biomarkers in drug discovery and development must comply with regulations regarding the validation and qualification of biomarkers, as well as legal frameworks for companion diagnostics. Data sharing should be secure and in accordance with GDPR.

Solution overview:

- Cooperation at national level to get information about how they are managing epidemiological data.
- Federated (EU) data approach.
- Define legal borders of bilateral data sharing (national laws/insurances vs. overarching research/databases).
- Public exchange to determine what are the ethical limitations of data sharing/collection with public and private companies.

Collaborators include: EBRAINS Knowledge Graph Group, European Commission Data Security Experts.

Summary

In conclusion, the rapid advancements in technology have opened new avenues for medical research, allowing for deeper exploration of physiological intricacies and their connection to diseases. However, such progress comes with critical considerations that need to be addressed for responsible, ethical, and effective implementation.

The introduction of advanced measurements and monitoring techniques presents several key challenges. Firstly, the complexity of the brain and its interconnections raises questions about the definition and scope of 'non-invasive' biomarkers, especially in comparison to their established use in other medical fields. It is proposed that this should be done in part by determining levels of invasiveness, both in terms of biological factors and societal implications. Secondly, ensuring responsible data sharing and access across the EU is essential. This requires addressing regulatory concerns, ensuring secure data sharing compliant with GDPR, and cooperation at the national level, federated EU data approaches, and the establishment of legal boundaries for data sharing. These solutions are proposed to create a harmonized and secure framework.

Lastly, involving patients and society in a meaningful and accessible manner is crucial to foster understanding, engagement, and support for these advancements, as well as ensuring meaningful consent to participation from patients or research subjects. To address the challenge of informed consent, strategies are proposed to simplify language and make it inclusive, provide education about the benefits of data sharing, create living labs for testing, and utilize platforms like EBRAINS Community to facilitate engagement.

These actions collectively aim to navigate the complex landscape of technological advancements and their ethical implications. By promoting clear definitions, secure data sharing, and informed engagement, the scientific community can ensure that these new depths of measurement contribute positively to medical research while safeguarding privacy and fostering public trust.

4. Integrating biomarkers and epidemiology

The epidemiological perspective: How should new biomarkers and epidemiological research be combined to best take advantage of the potential synergy? What novel insights can be produced by this integration, and how?

Introduction

The realm of brain health and mental disorders has gained global attention, fuelled by their escalating prevalence and societal impact. Among the key factors contributing to mental disorders and cognitive decline, stress has emerged as a prominent concern. The phenomenon of work-related stress, or burnout, has shown significant influence on individuals worldwide, prompting a need for effective interventions (Kalia, 2002; Sarner, 2018). As the urgency to comprehend brain health and mental disorders deepens, the integration of non-invasive biomarkers and epidemiology research emerges as an opportunity. The aim of this sub-topic is to explore the unparalleled potential that emerges from an integration of these disciplines. Our focus is twofold: How can the integration of novel biomarkers and comprehensive epidemiological research be best harnessed? And, what novel insights can this combination generate, shaping the future of our understanding and interventions?

Considering this opportunity, a series of objectives and actions have been outlined. The overarching objective is to start the discussion of how the integration of non-invasive biomarkers and epidemiology can illuminate brain diseases and mental disorders, offering avenues for identification and intervention. These objectives include:

- **Establishing Clear Definitions and Understanding of Non-Invasive Biomarkers:** The initial objective is to cultivate precise definitions of non-invasive biomarkers and discern how these markers contribute to insights across diverse populations. This clarity paves the way for identifying potential biomarkers related to brain health, laying the foundation for improved interpretation and intervention.
- **Leveraging Epidemiology for Non-Invasive Biomarker Research:** The second objective entails leveraging an epidemiological approach to gather data from expansive populations and diverse demographics. This approach enriches the qualitative and quantitative insights into brain health and mental disorders, supported by non-invasive biomarkers. By intertwining epidemiological data, researchers gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of these disorders across communities and demographics.

Furthermore, the exploration extends into the realm of diseases affecting the brain in later life, emphasizing the significance of early detection. A vision encompassing data integration and a multidisciplinary approach seeks to identify changes at the cellular level before manifesting as apparent diseases like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and multiple sclerosis. Such a venture necessitates a collaborative effort that transcends traditional disciplinary boundaries, involving experts in neuroscience, AI, epidemiology, and other related fields (molecularneurodegeneration.biomedcentral.com). This sub-topic aim to start the discussion on how to blend non-invasive biomarkers with epidemiology. As we venture into this new territory, our goal is to uncover new insights that can change how we understand and deal with brain health and mental disorders.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Action: Identification of pre-disease change in the brain

Challenge overview: A major action involves identifying specific biomarkers and developing a polysymptomatic picture of the disease that can indicate early preclinical changes at the cellular level before a disease becomes apparent. This requires data integration. Currently most research investigates diseases separately and it misses the underlying commonalities e.g., Alzheimer's, Parkinson's. A Data integration approach could better identify the early preclinical aspect of changes at the cellular level before the changes develop enough for a disease to become apparent.

Solution overview:

- Integrative approach: identification of specific biomarkers and development of a polysymptomatic picture of the disease (the set of symptoms, biomarkers) that identify the first changes at the biological

level before the disease occurs e.g., changes to microglia, changes related to chronic neuroinflammation.

- Create expert groups with experience in large scale studies (monitor populations every 10-15 years).
- Write a review of research that lends itself to this focus and present a paper. Eventually develop a conference around this subject.
- Have European Research Council (ERC) create funding e.g., through Horizon to create projects. On completion of a PhD, early career researchers should have the opportunity to undertake research across specialty areas. Most people work in a lab which has a narrow focus, and they follow predetermined modes of research methods and assumptions. Part of the training could be to identify candidates to train in integrating neuroscience results and advanced machine learning (ML) techniques. (A group in USA offer this).
- Recruit one well known neuroscientist to advocate for the focus.

Collaborators include: Neuroscientists with expertise in various diseases, AI specialists in machine learning, epidemiologists, and technology developers.

Characterisation of the action: Long development.

Resources: Those specializing in the brain, AI developers, epidemiologists, environmentally friendly computers.

Action: The role of cloud computing in data integration and big data (clarifying pros & cons)

Challenge overview: Given the importance of big data and data integration in brain health research, understanding the role of cloud computing is essential. However, this action requires addressing ethical implications and privacy concerns related to personal data in cloud computing. The challenge is the conflict in cloud computer use and privacy (access to personal data - nothing disappears from the internet = law level). Cloud computing does enable the creation of big data and the integration of population level data on biomarkers.

Solution overview:

- Identify the ethical implications of cloud computing. Identify weak links in the security chain and how this can be strengthened.
- Seek funding from groups involved in cloud computing.
- Have common database under EBRAINS infrastructure.

Collaborators include: Ethicists, AI specialists, cloud computing specialists, epidemiologists, legal representatives, EBRAINS.

Characterisation of the action: Project.

Resources: EBRAINS.

Action: “The scientific pathway”-approach. Assessment of biological to environment factors, lifestyle (physical environmental factors, nutrition, active life - physical activity).

Challenge overview: Data integration, data diversity: To gain a comprehensive understanding of brain health, researchers need to integrate diverse data related to biological, environmental, and lifestyle factors. The challenge, which also is part of the solution, is to go from the complex to the simple. Start with symptoms and then use technology to identify what is happening in the body e.g., consumer electronics (advance in smart watches (Heart Rate, quality of life, sleep, stress - implication of standard in data acquisition + validation for consumer electronics data), web tracking (anxiety, PTSD etc.) data, EEGs etc. and include the personal characteristics e.g. sex, and the external environmental impact to understand the “cause”.

Solution overview:

- Identify the steps along the pathway.

- Identify how each of the separate measures of changes in the body relate to each other. What would be differential diagnoses?
- Develop a theme at a neuroscience/multidisciplinary conference for one section of the conference.
- Write papers.
- Provide enough physical activities for all people but especially for neuro-patients.

Collaborators include: Ethicists, epidemiology, Technology developers, neuroscientists.

connect established expert networks.

Characterisation of the action: Long term.

Resources: Green computers (mega computers that have been developed to be environmentally aware), researchers, program developers.

Action: Apps - from data development to solutions

Challenge overview: Apps (platforms with personal data, localisation, type for living (active vs sedative), physiological data) provide/create big data to detect first sight of problems in the mental sphere and reasons for it.

Solution overview: New technologies, cloud computing, developing wearable devices to monitor different markers: to store and analyse big data. Validation in data acquisition. Standard in psycho surveys (elimination of subjectivity from data acquisition).

Collaborators include: Ethicists and lawyers, epidemiology, IT developers, psychiatrists, neurobiologists.

Characterisation of the action: Multiple projects.

Resources: App developers.

Action: Developing epidemiology driven study design

Challenge overview: Link epidemiology multimodal data and multiscale models with clinical scores/behaviour.

Solution overview: Infer multiscale biomarkers with data driven models.

Summary

In conclusion, the escalating prevalence and impact of brain health and mental disorders worldwide, exacerbated by stress and burnout, have sparked an urgent need for comprehensive research and interventions. Addressing this multifaceted challenge requires incorporating diverse disciplines and cutting-edge technologies. As such, a series of strategic objectives and actions have been outlined to synergize non-invasive biomarkers and epidemiology, effectively contributing to the identification, prevention, and management of brain diseases and mental disorders. To enhance the understanding of non-invasive biomarkers and their applications, the focus is on refining definitions and investigating how these markers intersect with diverse populations and scales. By aligning terminology and interpreting biomarker insights, researchers can better identify potential indicators related to brain health and mental disorders. Utilizing epidemiological methods in tandem with non-invasive biomarkers offers an opportunity to gather comprehensive data from large and diverse populations. This integration of data empowers researchers to gain nuanced insights into brain diseases and mental disorders across different demographics, fostering a more holistic understanding. The proposed actions within this sub-topic are meant to support these objectives. In essence, this integrative approach would be a significant leap in brain health research. By combining non-invasive biomarkers with epidemiology and leveraging advanced technologies, researchers are poised to create a comprehensive framework for identifying, understanding, and addressing brain diseases and mental disorders. The proposed actions emphasize the collaborative nature of this endeavour, calling for interdisciplinary partnerships that transcend boundaries and lead to groundbreaking advancements in brain health science.

5. Biomarker big data for early detection

The screening perspective: New biomarkers, expanded access to data, and improved epidemiology enable better screening for individuals. What types of biomarkers, data, and collaborations are needed to enable early detection of brain related diseases?

Introduction

To advance research in the field of brain health and mental disorders, it is essential to establish effective data sharing structures and collaborations that span across the European and international research communities. To achieve this goal, a comprehensive approach that involves various stakeholders is necessary.

One crucial aspect is the establishment of an EBRAINS/HBP data committee comprising neuroscientists, ethicists, neuroinformatic experts, and psychiatrists. This committee would play a central role in reaching out to the European research community and formulating guidelines, frameworks, and formatting standards for data sharing. Collaborating with international partners on data standards will further enhance data compatibility and accessibility.

The data should be categorised into several topics to facilitate efficient management and utilisation. Data collection from new sources and exploration of biomarker opportunities should be given priority. Leveraging existing structures such as the European Academy of Neurology and similar academies in psychiatry will help in ensuring data ownership and trust.

In the clinical context, prospective data collected should be prioritised for early detection biomarker big data. Local clinicians must have ownership of this data to ensure their involvement and trust in the process.

The transfer of data from the clinical context to the research context, integrating biomarkers and epidemiology, requires the involvement of local ethics committees. Here, EBRAINS can facilitate the creation of the necessary structures to streamline the process.

Efforts to change data structures should be focused on making data sharing more effective and avoiding legal hurdles. Strong project management will be essential to maintain the quality and progress of the initiatives. An important aspect that needs attention is to enable clinicians to submit data easily and effectively for wide data sharing. Developing a unified structure, platform, or set of standards for anonymisation before submitting data to a shared platform could be achieved through a well-funded call that brings together developers to work collaboratively. However, this process may require time, possibly taking one to five years or more.

It is important to acknowledge that scale harmonisation and development have different requirements across the research and clinical contexts. While scales can be developed in the research context, adapting them for clinical use takes time and careful consideration.

By addressing these aspects and fostering collaborations among researchers, clinicians, ethicists, and data experts, we can enhance data sharing, accelerate research, and ultimately contribute to the improvement of brain health and mental disorder treatments.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Action: Data integration

Challenge overview: Combining and integrating data from multiple sources can be challenging, especially when dealing with large and complex datasets.

Solution overview:

- Develop standards/plans for Data management specific to each new biomarker.
- Use standard, open, and accessible metadata to create models (such as EBRAINS associated) and common standards for neuroscience data.

- Integrate neuroscience data using EBRAINS Digital Brain Models (Atlases and so on) service and evaluate the accessibility and ease of use of such integration.
- Implementing strong data privacy and security measures to protect patient data and ensure that it is used responsibly and ethically.
- Setting standards for access to sensitive data.
- Developing advanced data integration methods and technologies to enable the efficient and effective integration of data from diverse sources.

Collaborators include: EBRAINS Knowledge Graph (<https://docs.kg.ebrains.eu/index.html>), associated institutes, Unis.

Characterisation of the action: Integrating parameters across clinical trials and associated genetic, gene expression, protein, and neuroimaging data.

Action: Data access

Challenge overview: Ensuring that researchers have access to the data they need while also protecting patient privacy and confidentiality can be challenging.

Solution overview:

- Use EBRAINS Data and Knowledge Service to aggregate big brain data. Promoting collaboration and data sharing among researchers to advance research in this field while also ensuring that data is used responsibly and ethically.
- Develop and implement standards to store raw data in open formats, evaluate the quality of the raw data and set restrictions (standards) to gain access to sensitive data (personality data).

Collaborators include: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/big-data>, EBRAINS, INCF.

Action: Data use

Challenge overview: Ensuring that data is used responsibly and ethically, and that the benefits of using big data are balanced against potential risks and harms. (Have continuous assessment of the processes).

Solution overview:

- Link epidemiology, multimodal big data and multiscale models with clinical scores/behaviour.
- To ensure that data is used responsibly and ethically, it is important to have clear guidelines and regulations in place governing the use of Big Data in research.
- This can include requirements for informed consent, transparency, and accountability. Ensuring transparency in the use of big data, including providing clear information to patients about how their data is being used and giving them control over their data.
- Based on technological advances (measuring/recording devices in society) and progress in understanding brain functioning. disorders mechanisms, to integrate data from various neurophysiological, and biochemical methods to create complex markers of states, and functions (re-understanding Health, Disease) - from simple to complex composite markers that describe spatiotemporal aspects of functioning (key markers - structure-function units, networks, units of neural circuit operations).

Collaborators include: Policymakers, University administrations, tech companies.

Action: Early detection, intervention, treatment, prevention

Challenge overview: Identifying and validating biomarkers (development of analysis methods in dynamics individually with involvement Big Data) that can be used for early detection and intervention can be challenging but has the potential to significantly improve patient outcomes.

Solution overview:

- To improve the identification and validation of biomarkers for early detection and intervention, it may be helpful to promote collaboration and data sharing among researchers. This can help to accelerate the discovery and validation process and improve patient outcomes.
- Design frameworks where early symptoms can be associated with as many medical scenarios as possible.
- Devise decision-support systems to support early detection and recommend suitable interventions.

Collaborators include: Researchers, Researcher networks, journals.

Summary

In conclusion, advancing research in the realm of brain health and mental disorders necessitates a robust foundation of effective data sharing structures and wide-ranging collaborations that extend across both European and international research communities. This undertaking requires a comprehensive and collective approach, drawing upon the expertise of various stakeholders.

Central to this effort is the establishment of an EBRAINS/Human Brain Project (HBP) data committee comprised of specialists in neuroscience, ethics, neuroinformatics, and psychiatry. This committee would play a pivotal role in formulating guidelines, frameworks, and formatting standards for data sharing. Collaborating with international partners to establish data standards would further enhance data compatibility and accessibility. Categorizing data into topics would streamline management, prioritizing new data sources and biomarker exploration. Local clinicians must have ownership of this data to ensure their engagement and trust. Transferring data from the clinical to research context necessitates the involvement of local ethics committees, where EBRAINS can facilitate the creation of necessary structures. Such transfer also requires a unified structure, platform, or set of standards for data anonymization before submission in to be effective. This could be achieved through well-funded calls that encourage collaborative development efforts. However, balancing scale harmonization and development across research and clinical contexts is pivotal. Developing scales for research and adapting them for clinical use requires thoughtful consideration and time.

By focusing on these critical aspects and fostering collaboration among researchers, clinicians, ethicists, and data experts, data sharing can be enhanced, research expedited, and brain health and mental disorder treatments improved. The proposed actions offer an approach to address the complexities of data integration, access, and responsible utilization, ultimately advancing our understanding and approach to brain health and mental disorders.

6. Pathways to practical outcomes of epidemiology

Better epidemiology and new biomarkers produce new insights and knowledge. Next steps could be to investigate causality, initiate programs for prevention, new policies for brain health, etc. How to ensure that these findings have broad and deep impact?

Introduction

In the pursuit of advancing the field of brain health and mental disorders, a multifaceted approach is required to address the challenges posed by missing and misaligned data, disparate assessment scales, and the need for effective implementation strategies. This comprehensive strategy should harmonize scales, integrate comprehensive health-related data, and address practical, financial, and technical aspects, all while fostering cooperation and compliance across multiple levels of healthcare and society.

Within this context, this sub-topic proposes several key actions to drive progress in various dimensions. The challenge of scale harmonization is recognized, where a lack of consensus in assessment scales hampers symptom quantification and stratification. To tackle this, a multidisciplinary approach involving AI third-party companies, healthcare software developers, and disease-specific associations is proposed. In tandem, the implementation of harmonized scales would require the expertise of clinicians, researchers, data scientists, and policymakers. Awareness campaigns, conferences, and working groups would facilitate this process.

The recording of practically useful and comprehensive health-related data would also be supported by introduction of unified pre-filled forms filled by patients before clinical visits, which could capture vital health, lifestyle, and environmental information. Collaboration with policymakers and enforcement mechanisms is crucial for successful implementation. In all these endeavours, the necessity to prioritize financial aspects should be considered. A robust financial controller, project manager, and risk assessment manager would ensure efficient resource allocation, realistic financial projections, and proactive risk management.

Cooperation and compliance present challenges at multiple levels. Clinicians' loyalty to familiar scales and the need for swift implementation of harmonized scales necessitate a concerted effort from expert groups, task forces, and the publication of high-impact studies. Furthermore, advocating for policy changes and preventive measures requires the engagement of officials, epidemiologists, and societal acceptance. Popularizing harmonized scales within the general populace, particularly in high-risk populations, would be driven through strategic campaigning initiatives and collaborations with societal stakeholders.

Ultimately, the actions of this sub-topic aim to start the discussion on how to enhance data sharing, harmonization of assessment scales, and make responsible integration of comprehensive health-related data, to ensure a more informed and cooperative approach to brain health and mental disorders, as well as a practical way to implementation.

Actions overview of the sub-topic

Action: Recording of comprehensive health-related data

Challenge overview: Lack of time for the treating physician to ask all health-related questions, environmental issues, lifestyle etc. such questionnaires would ideally be completed and then reviewed prior to the clinical consultation could facilitate the acquisition of such data and enable the registries to be pre-filled.

Solution overview: Necessity to create unified pre-filled forms to be filled by all patients before first visit of neurologist or psychiatrist.

Collaborators include: See above: enforcement by policymakers etc.

Characterisation of the action: Forms (digital, printed), feedback via questionnaires.

Resources: Low.

Action: Scale harmonisation (identification)

Challenge overview:

- Lacking consensus of assessment scales to quantify and stratify symptoms.

- The work of groups that already exist are not widely impactful.
- Difficulty of meta-analyses lies in scale.

Solution overview:

- Use of scales that assess the symptoms of patients.
- Researchers: seek funding for meta-analyses.

Collaborators include: Funders, researchers.

- AI third party companies.
- Healthcare software companies.
- Societies and associations for specific disease.

Characterisation of the action: AI projects, meta-analysis.

Resources: Highest in whole roadmap.

Action: Scale harmonisation (implementation)

Challenge overview: Clinical scale users tend to be ‘conservative’ and stick to familiar scales.

Solution overview:

- An expert group to reach consensus on the use of types of scales.
- Data scientists in supportive role for scale harmonization.

Collaborators include: Expert groups (clinicians and researchers), data scientists, policymakers.

Characterisation of the action: Awareness campaigns, conferences, small working groups.

Resources: High.

Action: Cooperation and compliance (level: policy/preventive measures)

Challenge overview: Policy changes and preventive measures pose financial efforts to governments and other-level institutions. For funding, show long-term economic implications and/or advantages arising from prevention which requires significant consensus, including, the strength of risk factors, and epidemiological prevalence etc. Novel interpretation, however, should always be considered, especially as new methods and methodologies are developed.

Solution overview: Repetitive meetings of officials and epidemiologists, the latter taking a consulting role in policy formation.

Collaborators include: Policymakers, societal acceptance.

Characterisation of the action: Campaigning initiatives.

Resources: Depends on campaigning method.

Action: Cooperation and compliance (level: scales being used in clinics)

Challenge overview: Consultation and treatment procedures are often conserved and hard to roll up according to a revised algorithm. i.e., clinicians often express strong loyalty towards a scale they have been used to. Harnessing acceptance and ensuring fast implementation of the harmonized scale is hence crucial and work should also aid data uniformity.

Solution overview: Expert group/task force that worked on scale harmonization should aim to produce high-impact publications and stimulate guidelines being established.

Collaborators include: Clinicians, policymakers, societies for guidance.

Characterisation of the action: Publications/case studies, upgradation of computing devices.

Resources: Medium

Summary

In the pursuit of advancing the field of brain health and mental disorders, a multifaceted approach is required to make outcomes useful in practice, and address the challenges posed by missing and misaligned data,

disparate assessment scales. This comprehensive strategy seeks to harmonize scales, integrate comprehensive health-related data, and address practical, financial, and technical aspects, all while fostering cooperation and compliance across multiple levels of healthcare and society.

Among other things, this requires scale harmonization, because a lack of consensus in assessment scales hampers symptom quantification and stratification. Here, a multidisciplinary approach involving AI third-party companies, healthcare software developers, and disease-specific associations is proposed to address this issue. In tandem, the implementation of these harmonized scales would require the expertise of clinicians, researchers, data scientists, and policymakers, as well as awareness campaigns, conferences, and working groups to ensure broad uptake. To support this action, the introduction of unified pre-filled forms filled by patients before clinical visits is also proposed. These could capture vital health, lifestyle, and environmental information.

Ultimately, these actions offer a roadmap to ensure the practical impact of all the sub-topics discussed in this report. Enhanced data sharing, harmonization of assessment scales, and the responsible integration of comprehensive health-related data will help to ensure a more informed and cooperative approach to brain health and mental disorders, that has real impact.

Concluding remarks

In the course of this report, an array of topics ranging from brain health and mental disorders to data sharing, neuroscience research, and epidemiology have been covered. The common thread that weaves through these diverse threads is the pursuit of knowledge, understanding, and progress in the realm of brain health.

The importance of collaborative efforts has emerged as a recurring theme. The complex challenges that the integration of non-invasive biomarkers and epidemiology for brain health present, cannot be tackled in isolation. From data committees comprising experts from various disciplines to fostering international collaborations through platforms like EBRAINS, the importance of partnerships is highlighted as pivotal for overcoming the challenges that this field presents. These partnerships extend beyond researchers and clinicians to include ethicists, data experts, policymakers, and even the wider society. Such collaborative endeavours emphasize the collective responsibility to advance brain health research and treatment.

Data has been showcased as a driving force for advancement. From sharing research data to integrating comprehensive health-related information, the utilization of data is a common underpinning of numerous proposed actions. A multifaceted approach is required to address the challenges posed by missing and misaligned data, disparate assessment scales, and the need for effective implementation strategies. This comprehensive strategy should harmonize scales, integrate comprehensive health-related data, and address practical, financial, and technical aspects, all while fostering cooperation and compliance across multiple levels of healthcare and society. The power of technology, especially AI, shines through as a catalyst for efficient data analysis, pattern recognition, and the development of innovative solutions within the space of non-invasive biomarkers.

The pursuit of the brain and its relationship with the body of the individual, as well as the person's location within society will be developed by ensuring epidemiology has a more inclusive role in research is at the heart of this report. In all sub-topics within this report, examples like the calls for integrating biomarkers more tightly in practice, addressing stigma, or advancing awareness initiatives, illustrate the overarching goal to create a holistic perspective that encompasses the intricacies of brain health and mental disorders.

The significance of communication and dissemination of knowledge also stands out. From raising awareness about brain disorders to sharing research findings, effective communication ensures that progress does not remain confined within individual research laboratories but extends to the broader research community, the public and decision-makers who can drive change.

In conclusion, it is evident that challenges remain in the realm of epidemiology and new biomarkers for brain health that cannot be solved in a report such as this. The journey toward solutions is multifaceted and require further development and specification as progress is made in this area. However, while the challenges are significant, this report sets out a blueprint for how progress might be made in this area. The collaboration and dedication of researchers, the advancements in technology, and the recognition of the potential within this area of research, promise a brighter future for brain health research, diagnosis, and treatment. The pathways explored in this discussion pave the way for a more comprehensive, informed, and cooperative approach that holds the potential to transform the landscape of brain health and mental disorders with the use of epidemiological data and the development of biomarkers.

EBRAINS Community

This CoCreation event on Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders is organized by the EBRAINS Community Building Team. EBRAINS Community is a growing online community within neuroscience, brain medicine, and brain-related technology. Whether you are looking for other EBRAINS users, would like to engage in research facilitated by the EBRAINS services and tools, or find elements of neuroscience and brain-related technology interesting, the odds are you will find like-minded in the EBRAINS Community.

Sign up for EBRAINS Community

Follow the link below and you will be sent directly to the first destination of your journey, the sign-up page. Simply sign-up with your EBRAINS Account or with your e-mail and click 'Sign up as Member'. The next step is then to verify your e-mail address through an e-mail that will be sent directly to your e-mail inbox. Give it a few minutes and remember to check your spam folder!

When you have signed up as a member and logged in, it is time for you to start building your personal profile. You simply follow the steps that you will be presented when you access your profile:

1. First name
2. Surname
3. Choose a minimum of one field of interest

Now press '**Publish to EBRAINS**' and start using the features and functions! You can always access your profile at a later time to fill in additional information or edit your profile.

Join our *open* sub-community '**EBRAINS CoCreate & Unconference**' to connect and chat with fellow participants and be the first to receive information about our events!

Join the EBRAINS community here:

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Human Brain Project

Behind EBRAINS CoCreate

EBRAINS CoCreate on Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders is run by The Danish Board of Technology, a part of the Human Brain Project and EBRAINS Community Building Team

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